

Visiting the Margins.

INnovative **CULT**ural **ToUR**is**M** in European peripheries

This Project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement no. 101004552

Deliverable number: 5.2

Title: Final pilots report

Due date: April 2024 (M36)

Actual date of delivery to EC: April 2024

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Context

Partner responsible for the deliverable	UGR
Deliverable author(s)	María Teresa Bonet García (UGR), INCULTUM Pilot leaders
Deliverable version number	1.0
Dissemination Level	Public

History

Change log			
Version	Date	Author(s)	Reason for change
1.0	25-04-2024	José María Martín Civantos (UGR)	Internal review

Release approval

Version	Date	Name & organisation	Role
1.0	26-04-2024	María Teresa Bonet García (UGR)	Support and management team, WP5

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1. Introduction

This report has been prepared thanks to the collaboration of all the pilots. We consider it essential that their opinion on the work carried out be reflected in this final report. We have tried to follow the same outline to give coherence to the report, these points have been addressed to a greater or lesser extent by all pilots so each one has completed the following sections:

- the objectives achieved during the project, with emphasis on the innovative elements in each area
- the main products achieved in the project
- difficulties and challenges encountered during these years of the project
- how INCULTUM's action will improve the study areas.
- Description of the scientific or industrial (in the case of SMEs) breakthrough developed during the project.

Although the DOA specifies that this report will pay special attention to the impact produced in relation to the expected KPIs, in order to avoid repetition, we refer the reader to "[D7.3 Updated plan for the Impact, evaluation and exploitation of results](#)", where a thorough analysis is made. We will only add some final scores related to KPIs in the conclusions section. In this way we also reinforce the interaction generated between the WPs and the partners themselves, in which tasks and deliverables have been possible thanks to the great collaboration generated among all.

2. Final input from the pilots

Pilot #1: Desert land and oasis: Altiplano de Granada (Spain-UGR)¹

1. The objectives achieved / innovative elements among the project:

- Use of the paths adjacent to the irrigation channels for the development of approved cultural routes.
- Recovery and maintenance of irrigated agricultural areas in the province of Granada through participatory and volunteer activities.
- Payment for environmental services agreements between municipalities and irrigation communities.
- Mediation between irrigation communities and public administrations (town councils, confederations, natural and national parks, etc.).

¹ UGR's team: Elena Correa Jiménez, M^a Teresa Bonet García and José María Martín Civantos.

2. The main products achieved

Five approved cultural routes, included in the network of official footpaths of the Andalusian Mountaineering Federation:

Figure 1. Example of an official sign for the Granada Geopark trail (case of trail in Zújar).

1. Acequias and Fuentes de Zújar Path:
<https://zenodo.org/records/10957072>
2. Acequias Paulo and El Coto trail in Pórtugos:
<https://zenodo.org/records/10910372>
3. Barjas irrigation ditch trail in Cáñar:
<https://zenodo.org/records/10910339>
4. Vega de Tubos trail (Castriil) irrigation ditches:
<https://zenodo.org/records/10910356>
5. Acequia de Alcázar (Jérez del Marquesado):
<https://zenodo.org/records/10910307>

Two payment for services agreements achieved:

1. Community of irrigators and Castril Town Council
2. Community of irrigators and Cáñar Town Council
(<https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/incultum-pilot-collaboration-agreements-established-in-altiplano-de-granada/>)

It should be emphasised that negotiations are currently underway for the signing of agreements between other irrigation communities and their respective town councils, as in the case of Jérez del Marquesado, Benamaurel and Zújar. As we shall see in the section on challenges, the bureaucratic and internal management complications of these bodies are slowing down the culmination of these agreements. But we are sure that in the very near future they will materialise in the protection of the historical irrigation systems of these municipalities.

Recovery of three different historical irrigation systems:

1. Acequia de Aynadamar, one of the main canalisations of Granada capital (<https://es.wikiloc.com/rutas-senderismo/sendero-acequia-de-aynadamar-tramo-el-fargue-campus-de-cartuja-137863729>).
2. Acequia de la Alpanchía, an abandoned irrigation system in a municipality of the Geopark, known as Galera. This recovery has been promoted by two local associations: PASOS and the Asociación Cultural de la Alpanchía (<https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/recovery-of-alpanchia-irrigation-channel/>).
3. Acequia de Alcázar and its irrigated area: recovery of a branch of the Alcázar irrigation channel and the irrigated area made up of cultivation terraces made of dry stone walls. <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/recovering-abandoned-spaces-at-the-dry-stone-balates-school-jerez-del-marquesado-granada/>

Organisation of 6 campaigns to clean historic irrigation ditches in the province of Granada:

1. Cleaning of the irrigation ditches of La Villa (Jérez del Marquesado, Granada) (2022) (<https://canal.ugr.es/noticia/limpieza-acequias-de-la-villa-en-jerez-del-marquesado-memolabugr/>)
2. Cleaning of the Barjas irrigation ditch (Cáñar, Granada) (2022)
3. Cleaning of the Barranco de Poqueira irrigation ditch (2022): (<https://canal.ugr.es/noticia/limpieza-de-la-acequia-nueva-del-barranco-de-poqueira-la-alpujarra-granada/#:~:text=31%2F03%2F2022&text=Los%20pr%C3%B3ximos%20d%C3%ADas%20%20y,coordinado%20por%20el%20profesor%20Dr.>)
4. Cleaning of the Barjas ditch (Cáñar, Granada) (2023): (<https://elcomarcaldelaalpujarra.com/un-grupo-de-voluntarios-limpian-la-acequia-baja-de-pitres-con-tecnicas-tradicionales/>)
5. Cleaning of the irrigation ditch Baja (Pitres, Granada)(2023)
6. Cleaning of the Jaufí irrigation ditch (Benamaurel, Granada) (2024)

Impact of our activities at international level

- Facing a Future of Drought, Spain Turns to Medieval Solutions and 'Ancient Wisdom': [New York Times](#)
- Barra's return of the Wild: [Acequias film \(BBC\)](#)

3. Difficulties and challenges encountered

We could divide the difficulties according to the actions carried out; on the one hand, the agreements on payment for services between Irrigation Communities and Municipalities are a tool to create a more institutional and official relationship between two organisations that already have a relationship, in many cases, informal. Also to generate some debate and proposals between the two institutions. This informal relationship between the two is, in part, the reason why the processes for reaching agreements are also very slow and, in some cases, do not lead to the final signature. What is also important is the generation of this debate and the acquisition of tools by the members of the irrigation communities, which is sometimes scarce.

There have been two agreements signed, but with all the municipalities in which we have worked, these agreements have been worked on, generating a certain amount of debate and proposals between town councils and irrigation communities, which we hope will soon reach agreements.

In the case of cultural trails, these two institutions also come into play: town councils and irrigation communities. For the approval of the trails, a fairly extensive bureaucratic process is necessary, which results in a slowing down of the signposting and approval process. This has meant that the signposting process has been very slow and has been extended until the last months of the project and has not allowed us to homologate any more trails, as planned.

4. How Pilot's action improve the study area

With the routes generated from the historic irrigation canals we will achieve the expansion of the tourist offer at different levels, at local level in each municipality and each irrigation community; also at Geopark level: this has resulted in the diversification of tourism and in the change of vision towards tourism: putting the local population and farmers at the centre, looking for their benefit, not the tourist. This will also be a development of the tourism offer at the provincial level, thanks also to the diffusion carried out through the Provincial Tourism Board of Granada. In the same vein, these routes will benefit the inclusion of the vegas (understood as "oasis" in the desert) in the cultural offerings of the Geopark, beyond the caves and badlands. Collaboration with the irrigation communities and their involvement in the creation of the routes also implies that visitors should understand these meadows as a living cultivation area that generates wealth beyond a tremendously attractive visual space. The irrigation and cultivation areas generated by the historical and

traditional irrigation systems (the vegas) are the culmination of centuries of traditional knowledge (TEK) and environmentally sustainable areas.

The protection of these areas, the empowerment of irrigation and local communities and the enrichment of municipalities through this protection is what we have achieved with the service agreements. These agreements therefore represent innovative tools in land management and the protection of historical irrigation systems: stewardship agreements and administrative agreements on payment for ecosystem services are the most innovative and improve action in the pilot #1.

On the other hand, these improvements in the protection of historical irrigation systems through payment for services agreements could be extended to other areas not covered by the project. This is the case of the municipality of Galera and our close collaboration with the Alpanchía Association, who, after seeing the good results in other areas, asked to be included in our area. This collaboration with the association will soon bear fruit with the recovery of the vega area through the creation of a cultural route.

Pilot #2: Agrarian coastal plain: Campina de Faro (Portugal- UAAlg)²

1. The objectives achieved / innovative elements among the project:

- Catalogue of water heritage with photographic survey, drawn (manual and digital), and mapped at various scales.
- Inventory of stakeholders and others interested parties in valorizing the heritage as a factor in local development.
- Elaboration of 3 projects to recovery the landscape and hydro-agricultural heritage.
- Integration of teaching and research (fieldwork, territorial intervention proposals and 3 master's theses).
- Participatory map: the cultural routes based on water heritage are being designed in collaboration with stakeholders to be guided by local farmers and small tourism business. We used the knowledge of older inhabitants about the landscape and material and immaterial heritage, authentic guardians of memory, having the Storytelling method and Story Map as a support for the cultural routes as a vector of territorial and social cohesion.
- Participatory workshops on how to build a cultural tourism itinerary and product.

² University of Algarve's team: Desidério Batista, Manuela Guerreiro, Bernardete Sequeira, Miguel Reimão Costa, Marisa Cesário, Dora Agapito and Filipe Neto. From the PRO Loco: Artur Gregório, Ana Arsénio and Vânia Martins.

- Design/cocreation of Campina de Faro as a smart territory connecting agroecology and agrotourism through an active and collaborative heritage community.

2. The main products achieved

Figure 2. A noria in pilot #2

- Mapping and photographic survey of more than 400 hydraulic structures, and architectural survey and digital drawing of 21 water heritage sites and 42 structures.

- Proposal of 5 water heritage routes (3 carbon-neutral, by walking and bicycle, of which 1 using GPS; and 2 for motorised vehicles).
- Participatory-collaborative heritage education actions (3) and heritage intervention relating to the recovery of the water heritage/historic irrigation system (2).
- Organisation of 3 scientific events (seminars and conferences) and 2 training activities (participatory workshops), and presentation of the pilot at 10 scientific events (5 national and 5 international).
- Publication of 2 articles in international journals, 3 book chapters (1 national and 2 international) and preparation of 2 books (1 to be published this year and another in 2025). Some of these publications are in the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#)
- Conducting interviews with 20 farmers (15 structured interviews and 5 open interviews, recorded), and conducting 1 questionnaire on the perception of cultural routes, answered online by 134 people (visitors and residents). These metadata are included in the [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#)

3. Difficulties and challenges encountered

The main difficulties encountered were related to three different issues. Firstly, the bureaucratic aspects associated with project management at local level. Secondly, the lack of information on the water heritage and the lack of knowledge of its diversity and complexity on the part of the public administration. And thirdly, the

difficulty in accessing the water assets as they are private (unlike other pilots where they are public, as in pilot #1 Altiplano de Granada), always requiring prior authorisation from the owners. Therefore, to carry out the fieldwork, it was always necessary to contact the farm owners and/or tenant farmers in advance. This process delayed the visits and the reconnaissance and survey of the heritage. But, on the other hand, it allowed direct contact with the local community and the collection of oral information about traditional cultivation and irrigation techniques. The biggest challenge facing our work was twofold. On the one hand, regarding historical research, understanding the role and importance of the traditional irrigation system in the social and economic development of the study area and the reasons that led to its disuse and abandonment.

On the other hand, how to tackle its study and cataloguing as a condition for safeguarding and enhancing this heritage (in an accelerated process of degradation), through the participation-collaboration of the local community. Their contribution proved to be fundamental. The recognition of the historical interest and cultural and environmental value of the old irrigation system, and the enthusiasm shown by the farmers for its recovery and subsequent management of the cultural routes, was very important in validating our expectations and continuing our work.

The participatory map, based on reactivating collective memory for a future with a past, reflects the community's emotional attachment to the landscape and heritage, and its importance for the future of Campina in the context of community-based cultural tourism. In fact, the future of study area requires landscape and water heritage based-solutions as a support for community-based cultural tourism, that is expressed in the participation-collaboration of residents in the creation of benefits for the whole community.

4. How Pilot's action improve the study area

The actions carried out will make a decisive contribution to (re)qualifying the agrarian landscape and improving the quality of life of the resident and visiting population. These actions were based on the following intervention principle: Know first to intervene later. In this sense, and in view of the landscape degradation that has taken place in recent decades, it was considered essential to inventory, recover, and valorize the cultural heritage, both tangible and intangible, to help reverse the situation. This was the case with the participatory-collaborative study of water heritage, with the aim of this heritage becoming visible and protagonist, integrated into cultural routes managed by the community itself.

These routes not only include guided tours of their farms by farmers, but also connect local producers' markets, based on production-sale-consumption proximity circuits, and traditional food restaurants (Mediterranean diet), with immediate

returns for the local economy. This is a collaborative economy in which cultural tourism is a privileged tool for social intervention.

The different actions (education and training, heritage intervention, communication and dissemination, etc.) based on the participatory-collaborative approach will contribute to fulfilling the objectives of sustainable development, through the promotion of sustainable communities, sustainable production and consumption, and the protection of terrestrial life, among others.

These actions, framed within the ecological transition in which reducing the water footprint, promoting regenerative agriculture and short circuits are essential, will make a decisive contribution to the socio-cultural, economic, and environmental sustainability of the study area.

On the other hand, the activities and actions carried out have made it possible to deepen and consolidate relations between the scientific community, stakeholders, and residents, facilitating the pursuit of the pilot's objectives and fostering new partnerships for future projects in the study area.

5. Description of the scientific breakthrough developed during the project

The study of water heritage, based on a methodology that combines historical research and bibliographical sources with fieldwork, has enabled the identification and typological characterization of the *norias*. The typological diversity catalogued, based on the design of the gear and its operation (animal traction, motor, and pump, aeroengine, etc.), the construction processes and materials used, is unprecedented. This typological classification has contributed to the advancement of scientific knowledge about these historic hydraulic structures.

The development of standardized water heritage restoration projects based on traditional construction materials, techniques, and processes, according to the typological classification and construction period, is also innovative and could inspire and be a benchmark for water heritage restoration interventions in other geographical and cultural contexts.

The participatory-collaborative approach used has been published and has the potential to be trialed and experimented with in other community-based cultural tourism projects.

Pilot #3: Mining treasures of Central Slovakia: Banska Bystrica and Central Sloakia (Slovakia-UMB)³

The Banská Bystrica Self-Governing Region is the country's largest region. It shares its southern border with the Republic of Hungary. The region's topography is

³ UMB's team is composed by Alexandra Bitusikova, Kamila Borsekova and Rojikova Darina

diverse, ranging from high mountains in the north, rugged landscapes in the center, to gently rolling and flat areas in the south. With a population of approximately 660,000, the Banská Bystrica Self-Governing Region has a population density of fewer than 70 inhabitants per km². Once considered the most prosperous and affluent region in Slovakia, it now ranks among the least developed. This decline is evident from its relatively high unemployment rate and low GDP. Despite the region's rich cultural and natural assets, a significant portion of its population is employed in the industrial, trade, and construction sectors. Mining (related to copper, silver and gold mining), a pivotal industry primarily in the Middle Ages, has seen a decline, with the focus now primarily on surface mining of non-metallic minerals. Although there are still numerous significant remains of mining activities, the tourism sector in the Banská Bystrica Self-Governing Region is underdeveloped.

Banská Bystrica and Banská Štiavnica – the main mining cities (and research sites) along with their surrounding municipalities, are distinguished by over 600 tangible and industrial heritage sites that stand testament to their rich mining history. This cultural heritage, intertwined with the region's stunning natural landscapes and punctuated by cultural routes like the Barbora Route and the European Fugger's Route, establishes Central Slovakia's unique competitive advantage. By harnessing and effectively leveraging this shared competitive advantage, mining towns and tourist routes can significantly bolster the region's sustainable development. The Barbora and the Fugger Routes present a prime opportunity for such development. By harnessing wider participation from local communities and beyond, these routes can be transformed into vibrant hubs of sustainable tourism, ensuring their preservation and relevance for generations to come.

1. The objectives achieved / innovative elements among the project

The objective of the pilot was to create an interactive digital platform about mining treasures in mining towns in central Slovakia, which intersects two tourist routes in the northern part of the Banská Bystrica self-governing region in central Slovakia, including the mining towns of Banská Bystrica. and Banská Štiavnica (UNESCO World Heritage Site). The most important mining locations are presented on one responsive platform. This platform was developed to bolster regional development and tourism in Slovakia's largest Banska Bystrica Self-Governing Region, particularly in the more underdeveloped and marginalized areas of the region. Its creation was rooted in a participatory approach, involving close collaboration with various stakeholders and individuals. This pilot also aims to contribute to the creation of awareness about importance and significance of the cultural heritage associated with mining in central Slovakia and empower building a mining heritage community in Slovakia.

2. Actions and methods

The platform is a living organism that has been built through a number of actions and methods:

- **Data collection:** During the development of the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform, extensive [primary](#) and [secondary data](#) (both available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community) were collected and evaluated to inform its creation, testing, usage, and promotion. This included visiting over 30 museums and galleries, inspecting 60 tangible heritage sites, exploring 40 industrial heritage sites, and attending 25 events related to mining. Additionally, more than 250 texts were prepared and reviewed for the platform's content, over 2,300 photos were taken, and approximately 350 websites were surveyed for inspiration. In total, more than 100 people contributed to the data collection process for the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform.
- **Community engagement:** During the initial stages of developing the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" interactive platform, crucial meetings were held with key stakeholders, including the Regional Destination Management Organization BBSK and the Central Slovakian Local Destination Management Organization. Additionally, over 20 meetings were organized with the ICT company involved in preparing the digital platform.
In 2023, collaboration was extended to stakeholders deeply engaged in preserving and advancing mining heritage for sustainable tourism and product innovation. This included partnerships with CA Terra Montanae, CA Štiavnický tajch, Maximilian Hella Štiavnické Bane Primary School, CA Špaňodolinská Historical School, and the Slovak Mining Museum in Banská Štiavnica. Particularly close cooperation was forged with CA Terra Montanae, focusing on the Barbora Route project. Subsequently, in August 2023, a [Memorandum of Cooperation](#) was signed with representatives from CA Terra Montanae, marking a significant milestone in the collaborative efforts towards the creation of an interactive platform and future endeavours.
- **Creation and design of responsive platform – technical part:** The technical development of the platform was carried out in three main phases. In the first phase, the information architecture was established based on specified requirements, followed by the design of necessary subpages, modules, and elements, and the deployment of front-end and back-end systems. The second phase involved integrating a new visual identity, making design modifications, deploying demo content such as articles and static pages, preparing the content framework, and optimizing SEO, along with creating a comprehensive manual for cloud content architecture and conducting a two-phase training program using TYPO3. The final phase focused on configuring the content management system for language mutations, setting up recording elements for translation (activities, articles, tags, etc.), configuring route interconnections, setting up

Google Analytics, creating and implementing language files for translation, and integrating additional filters like route complexity.

- **Creation and design of responsive platform – design and marketing part – logo competition, participatory approach to logo design and creation:** Students played a key role in designing the interactive platform's visual identity through a specific assignment related to the visual identity of the platform. Participation in creating the visual identity for the Mining Treasures platform was achieved in a participatory manner through a logo competition, in which a total of 31 students were involved. This competition led to the creation of 19 proposals for the visual identity, logo, and design manual of the interactive Mining Treasures platform. The winning logo was co-developed with students and an ICT company and is used in the Mining Treasures platform as part of the visual identity.
- **Creation of content for responsive platform – participatory approach to platform content development:** Creating content for an interactive platform involves several demanding tasks: compiling text from various sources, including books, articles, and community meetings; capturing and editing photographs; gathering information on entrance fees, opening hours, track lengths, and restrictions; and pinpointing exact locations using Google Maps coordinates, verified on-site. The content creation process is participatory, engaging students, representatives from partner organizations, and project-involved scientists. Over 25 authors and 30 photographers contributed to the creation of the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform's content. Additionally, more than 40 students aid in platform promotion by sharing posts on social media platforms like Facebook and Instagram.

3. Innovations of the pilot action Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia

- **Technical and product innovations (hard innovations):**
 - The technical part of the pilot action is characterized by a participatory approach, engaging a variety of stakeholders in the design and content development processes.
 - Unique web platform has been developed, tailored specifically for mining heritage in Central Slovakia with an educational context. This platform not only facilitates the exploration of mining heritage but also introduces previously inaccessible localities to tourists.
- **Social innovations (soft innovations):**
 - Through the creation of unique educational content, the initiative aims to influence and potentially alter educational curricula, fostering a deeper understanding and appreciation of mining heritage in Central Slovakia and beyond.

- This pilot actively promotes networking, cooperation, and participation among a wide network of stakeholders from the public, private, and non-profit sectors, as well as individuals.
- The initiative is dedicated to empowering the mining heritage community and enhancing the development of Central Slovakia localities (including peripheral and marginalised areas) through cultural tourism that adheres to principles of both tourism sustainability and sustainable tourism.

These innovations collectively aim to preserve and promote the rich mining heritage of Central Slovakia while fostering a sustainable and inclusive approach to cultural tourism.

4. Main achievements and conclusion

Thanks to the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" pilot project, the region's mining sites are now showcased through an interactive platform and digital map. Launched in December 2022, this initiative adopted a participatory approach to enhance the current tourism offerings and encourage urban tourists to explore a broader area. The platform not only highlights well-known mining locations but also promotes lesser-known sites that were previously overlooked due to inadequate promotion by local tourist information centers, tourism organizations, and travel agencies.

The platform, which was officially launched on the website www.banickepoklady.eu, features 250 activities across nine categories, including galleries, museums, tangible and intangible heritage, industrial heritage, events, educational activities, children's activities, hiking, and on-the-map exploration. Since April 2023, an English version has been available, significantly extending its reach to international visitors. To date, the platform has attracted over 1,000 users from 25 different countries. The creation of the platform involved extensive participation from the community, including local, regional, and international tourists, stakeholders in tourism, local communities, students, and pupils.

More than 40 organizations across public, private, and non-profit sectors, 90 students from five academic courses, 27 photographers (including four professionals), and 22 active content authors contributed to the platform's development. Throughout the development process, over 45 meetings were held with these contributors.

Figure 3. Website front page

Data collection was a critical aspect of this project, with more than 100 people participating in gathering primary and secondary data. This data included texts, photographs, videos, and audio materials, which were essential for creating, testing, using, and promoting the platform. More than 30 museums and galleries, 60 tangible heritage objects, 40 industrial heritage objects, and 25 events were visited by the research team for data collection purposes. Additionally, the platform and its content have been actively promoted on social media platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and YouTube, using hashtags such as #banicképoklady and #miningtreasures.

Overall, the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform not only serves as a vibrant showcase of the region's significant mining sites but also as a testament to the collaborative and participatory effort involved in its creation, embodying a comprehensive approach to cultural and heritage tourism.

5. Steps forward

With the INCULTUM project, the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform is far from the end of its journey. We have succeeded in continuing the development of the platform through numerous activities and projects. In the future, we plan to include the third mining city in Central Slovakia—Kremnica—thereby enriching the platform with new and original content. Additionally, we are involved in a new Horizon Europe project, SECReTour, and will continue to work on the pilot. Main actions will include developing a business model for the Barbora route, creating original educational content, and enhancing entrepreneurial and cultural tourism activities connected to the mining heritage. Through another project, we plan to

design a physical map that includes a layer capable of interconnecting with the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform. These initiatives signify a robust commitment to expanding and enhancing the "Mining Treasures of Central Slovakia" platform, ensuring its continued evolution and impact on cultural and heritage tourism in the region. Additionally, these efforts help to foster the development of peripheral areas, bringing increased attention and resources to often overlooked locations.

Pilot #4: Sicilian Inland: Monti di Trapani (Italy- GAL Elimos)⁴

1. Context Analysis/Summary:

The Greenway represents the project to transform the disused railway line "Kaggera - Vita - Salemi" into a "greenway." The initiative focuses on the maintenance and safety of the entire route, transforming the old railway line into a cycling and pedestrian path. Thanks to initiatives promoted by INCULTUM, awareness regarding this transformation has increased, and several discussion opportunities have been organized, involving both the public and private sectors to expand the participation network.

Particular attention has been given to the inclusion of private actors, considering that some cultural and archaeological assets are located on private property. Agreements have been signed with organizations such as local action groups and associations as the greenway will extend to Selinunte, adding another 45 km to our initial 12 km. A team of experts in the history and culture of the territory is developing multilingual informative captions and brochures, in line with another initiative focused on Islamic-archaeological itineraries. The goal is to create a new tourist itinerary that crosses the western part of Sicily, generating new employment opportunities and a significant increase in local economic activity, as well as enhancing the tourism offer.

All these actions have been implemented following a bottom-up approach, based on active community participation, in line with the action ideology of GAL ELIMOS.

2. Main Results of the GREENWAY Project

- **Cultural Tourism Products:**

The GREENWAY project is generating a series of unique cultural tourism products, focused on enhancing Sicily's historical and cultural heritage through the redevelopment of the "Kaggera-Vita-Salemi" railway line. The information

⁴ GAL Elimos team: Rocco Lima, Anna Valk and Maurilio Caracci

about this Greenway is already available in [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#). The main results in this area include:

- **Greenway as a Tourist Itinerary:** The transformation of the railway line into a greenway has created a unique tourist itinerary, enriched with informative signs and captions along the route. Visitors can now explore the scenic and historical beauty of Sicily through a sustainable tourism experience.
- **High-Quality Information Brochures:** Through paid contracts with experts in Islamic culture and archaeology, high-quality informative brochures have been drafted. These brochures provide cultural and historical insights along the Greenway, enriching tourists' experience and promoting greater awareness of the heritage. These brochures are also in Zenodo INCULTUM Community: <https://zenodo.org/records/10944233> and <https://zenodo.org/records/10944204>

- **Partnership for Innovation:** The innovative extension of the Greenway through agreements with another local action group has created a broader tourist network on the island. This collaboration not only expands tourism opportunities but also contributes to greater diversification of cultural and tourism offerings through new initiatives.

- **Community-Related Outcome:**

The active involvement of the local community is a key element of the GREENWAY project and has significant impacts on the lives and awareness of the population over a wide area. The main results in this context include:

- **Increased Heritage Awareness:** The project has raised awareness among local communities and tourists about the richness of the territory's historical and cultural heritage. The Greenway not only connects places of interest but also contributes to greater awareness of local history and culture.
- **Increase in Tourist Flow:** Thanks to sustainable hiking offers, the community is experiencing a significant increase in tourist flow. This has a positive impact on the local economy, fostering the growth of commercial activities and tourist services.
- **Heritage Conservation:** The active participation of the community in safeguarding the historical and cultural heritage is evident in the enhancement of archaeological artifacts along the route. These efforts contribute to preserving collective memory and ensuring greater livability of the territory, as well as being sustainable.

- **Method/Tool-Related Outcome:**

The GREENWAY project has adopted an innovative and sustainable approach in pursuing its objectives. Key results related to the method/tool include:

- **Conversion of Railway Line into Greenway:** The transformation of the railway line into a Greenway represents a sustainable method for reusing disused resources. The approach of "sustainable mobility and slow tourism" offers a low environmental impact alternative, while promoting sustainable tourism.
- **Active Collaboration with Experts and Associations:** Active collaboration with experts in Islamic culture, archaeology, hiking, and local associations has been crucial for drafting informative brochures and enriching the tourist experience. This method has ensured an accurate and informative approach.
- **Sustainability as a Guide:** Sustainability has been the guiding principle of the project, balancing economic, social, and environmental needs. This method has allowed for the realization of a project that not only promotes sustainable tourism but also contributes to the balanced development of the local territory.

3. Future Perspectives: Results (Short and Medium Term)

Contracts for Services as Development Tools:

Our GREENWAY project has been enthusiastically welcomed by the local communities of Calatafimi Segesta and Vita, demonstrating growing interest not only in the originally involved centers but also from other surrounding areas. The possibility of extending the project to new territories has emerged, with informational requests from other GALs, reinforcing the idea that project actions are spreading well beyond the initial implementation area.

Destination Branding:

Recognition and approval of our GREENWAY route by Sicilian regional and tourism authorities are ongoing. This homologation process will help promote our destination, attracting new types of visitors and creating a distinctive identity for the GREENWAY. Collaborations with tourism entities and specialized hiking organizations will be crucial for targeted promotion and the creation of tourist packages to be included in the broader offer of the Sicilian region, adding new opportunities for tourists who appreciate slow and mindful enjoyment of the local cultural heritage.

Community Building and Destination Enhancement:

Through the creation of new narratives and the attraction of diversified visitors, our project aims to empower the local community and enhance the destination. Collaborations with national federations and targeted promotion will contribute to ensuring visibility and notoriety for the GREENWAY, positioning it as a valuable destination and offering an open-air museum through which local residents become actors of the ecological transition.

Affirming the Landscape as a Common Good:

GREENWAY maintenance actions demonstrate local sustainable practices and contribute to strengthening the community's attachment to shared values. The landscape approach of our project is a catalyst for sustainable projects, involving local representatives and creating a heritage community. Debates on heritage management and community accountability will strengthen the role of the landscape as a common good.

Creating Social Bonds:

The territory already boasts numerous cultural events in prestigious locations such as the theater of Segesta, Erice, Trapani, etc. To this circuit, additional events, cultural activities, and festivals can be added to promote social cohesion and resident participation. The organization of periodic initiatives is designed to institutionalize the common heritage in local cultural policy, creating an annual tradition and further consolidating social bonds.

Connecting Productive Economy with Tourism and Landscape Management:

Our project promotes the diversification of agricultural activities and the improvement of service offerings. Collaborations with the agricultural sector promote sustainability and the provision of services aimed at meeting slow tourism needs.

Increase in Tourist Flow and Awareness:

- Implement targeted marketing campaigns to promote sustainable hiking offerings through online channels and social media.
- Organize local promotional events to engage the community and increase awareness of the heritage.
- Introduce awareness programs in local schools to involve young people in the historical and cultural heritage.

Continued Enhancement of Archaeological Artifacts:

- Plan specific recovery interventions for artifacts along the Greenway, involving entrepreneurs and experts from related sectors.
- Initiate collaborations with cultural institutions to host temporary exhibitions or contemporary art installations at sites located near the route and along the route itself.

Expansion of Innovations and Partnerships:

- Strengthen collaborations with other GALs to extend the Greenway to new areas, creating a regional tourist network.
- Explore new partnerships with environmental organizations and sustainable tourism for further joint initiatives and projects.

Development of Cultural Tourism Products:

- Introduce new tourist packages that include unique cultural experiences along the greenway, such as themed guided tours or artistic activities.
- Engage local tourist operators in the development of customized itineraries based on specific visitor interests.

4. Future Perspectives: Impact (Medium and Long Term)

Spread of contract signing for services:

The success of our contract model and associated negotiations could inspire communities in other regions, offering an innovative approach to engaging local communities in sustainable development processes.

Spread of the innovative integrated method for territorial entrepreneurship:

The GREENWAY route can become a catalyst for other landscape initiatives, offering an innovative method to federate economic, social, and cultural activities. The methodology adopted can be used as a model in other territories.

Spread of the model to other cultural sectors:

Adoption could represent a successful model to replicate in other contexts, creating broader collaboration and community empowerment in the production of cultural programs.

Towards other common goods:

Our innovative and sustainable approach is already inspiring future projects, such as the one centered on thermal waters as a common good, which GAL Elimos is also pursuing at the political level to enhance an as yet unexpressed heritage of the Region. The methodology and experience gained in our project

can be applied to other common goods, contributing to promoting sustainable development.

Eligibility for external funding:

We plan to submit additional funding requests to the European Union, based on the positive experience of our GREENWAY project. Inclusion in new EU funding programs will demonstrate recognition of implemented actions and the validity of our approach.

Policy-related impact as 'best practice':

Our GREENWAY project is set to become a recognized "best practice," cited in publications and regional policies as a successful example of sustainable exploitation of local heritage.

Sustainable Growth of the Local Economy:

- Monitor the medium-term economic impact of the project, focusing on increased revenues for local businesses and employment in the tourism sector.
- Explore additional funding opportunities to support further economic development of the territory.

Consolidation of the Role as a Sustainable Tourism Destination:

- Obtain recognitions and certifications for the Greenway as a sustainable tourist destination.
- Collaborate with national and international organizations to promote the Greenway as a successful model of sustainable redevelopment.

Promotion of Community Involvement:

- Implement environmental education initiatives to involve the community in the long-term maintenance and management of the Greenway.
- Create volunteer programs to encourage ongoing community participation in the maintenance and enrichment of the Greenway.

Expansion of the Model to Other Regions:

- Document and share best practices from the GREENWAY project with other interested regions, promoting replicability of the model in similar contexts.
- Participate in tourism sector fairs and national and international conferences to present the project as a successful case study in sustainable redevelopment and cultural tourism and to promote its enjoyment."

Pilot #5: Tuscan-Emilian Apennines. Garfagnana (Italy-UNIFI)⁵

1. The objectives achieved

The INCULTUM project seeks to revitalise San Pellegrino in Alpe by leveraging storytelling as a catalyst for social and cultural rejuvenation. By reconnecting residents with their heritage and engaging new generations, the project aims to reignite interest in the region's history and culture. The integration of narratives into tourism strategies facilitates a deeper connection between visitors and the destination, fostering memorable experiences and preserving authenticity. To bridge the generational gap, the project employs modern technologies, such as augmented reality, to enhance the museum experience and make historical artefacts accessible to digital-native audiences. In this context, a theatrical performance brings museum collections to life, while technological upgrades ensure continued innovation beyond the project's duration. This approach aligns with contemporary tourism trends, which prioritise unique experiences and immersive storytelling.

2. Tasks accomplished and products, focusing on innovations

The objectives of the INCULTUM project were multifaceted and aimed at enhancing cultural tourism in the San Pellegrino in Alpe area. These objectives included:

- Planning and participation in theatrical performances: The project aimed to create synergy between storytelling, identity practices, and tourist enhancement through theatrical performances centered around the history of the Provincial Ethnographic Museum "Don Luigi Pellegrini" and the parish priest to whom the museum is dedicated;
- Conceptualization and development of technological and multimedia devices within the Ethnographic Museum: the project sought to engage younger generations and make the museum more accessible and engaging through the installation of digital and multimedia systems;
- Interviews and surveys: data collection and information gathering, both qualitative and quantitative, were initiated to understand the perspectives of local operators, visitors, and students; these data are available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community: [Perception surveys to Ethnological Museum visitors](#)

⁵ UNIFI's team: Enrica Lemmi, Adele Cogno, Andrea Pedri and Martina Pirrone

[and theatrical performance - 2023 - San Pellegrino in Alpe \(Garfagnana\)](#) and also [Perception surveys to Ethnological Museum visitors - 2022 IT - San Pellegrino in Alpe \(Garfagnana\)](#)

- Development of a business plan: efforts were directed towards developing management perspectives related to the Ethnographic Museum of San Pellegrino in Alpe to gauge interest in supporting its future and to explore potential collaborations with other tourist operators.

3. Challenges

- San Pellegrino in Alpe faces complexities in its integration within tourist itineraries due to its high elevation and limited transportation access, exacerbated by harsh winter conditions. These factors result in a tourism drought for approximately nine months, perpetuating a cycle of seasonal operation and diminishing visitor interest. The decline in visitors to the Ethnographic Museum, specifically, reflects broader trends in tourism and local engagement in the area.
- Furthermore, the area's demographic decline exacerbates tourism challenges, as a dwindling population struggles to maintain the region's natural and cultural heritage. This depopulation threatens the sustainability of local management and the preservation of centuries-old traditions.
- During the duration of the project, given the small size of the hamlet, the number of local operators to include has always remained limited, although participation has been lively from everyone involved.
- The relationship with the administrations has not always been fruitful, and moreover, being a village shared between two municipalities, two negotiation tables had to be set up simultaneously.
- The search for funding to finance projects and new installations has required a lot of work and has not always led to positive results; in any case, the search has been directed towards both private entities such as foundations and banks and towards the public sector.

4. Further perspectives

The project's activities will enhance further studies in the area by providing valuable insights into the effectiveness of various strategies for cultural tourism

development. As evidenced by the data collected during the project, the storytelling-based strategy that was adopted yielded positive results.

The revitalization of a significant social institution like the Provincial Ethnographic Museum of San Pellegrino in Alpe could bolster a renewed sense of community identity. This, in turn, could foster resilience and consciousness within the local fabric, spurred by external interest driving innovation and reinterpretation of both tangible and intangible heritage. Through a narrative journey interwoven with local values and cultural legacy, coupled with advancements in technology and digital platforms, museums can undergo a rejuvenation process that bridges tradition with modernity. The prospect of immortalising narratives through digital mediums ensures perpetual accessibility for future generations, meeting the expectations of contemporary visitors accustomed to digital experiences.

Researchers can analyse the project's methodologies, outcomes, and challenges to inform future initiatives in similar contexts. Additionally, the project's focus on engaging local communities, leveraging technology, and collaborating with stakeholders can serve as a model for sustainable tourism development in other regions which are facing the same challenges. Overall, the project's contributions to knowledge dissemination, stakeholder engagement, and capacity building will facilitate ongoing research and development in cultural tourism.

Pilot #6: Bibracte-Morvan: Ancient paths into the future. Regional park of Morvan (France-Bibracte)⁶

1. The objectives achieved

Participation in INCULTUM has enabled the creation of an innovative territorial project, using the Grands Sites de France (GSF) landscape approach and the attachment of the inhabitants to their common landscape and their singular heritage as a vector for social cohesion and action.

By using sustainable cultural tourism as a tool of recognising and diversifying economic activities based on the resources of a shared landscape, Ancient Path to the Future is an innovative social initiative that strengthens regional synergies and enables tourism policy to be seen as more than just a facet of economic and residential attractiveness policy.

The focus on building a shared vision and mobilizing local players has been crucial for the success of this community-based project.

2. Main achievements and innovations:

⁶ Bibracte EPCC's team: Vincent Guichard and Flore Coppin

- **Building awareness of the cultural heritage of 1100+ km network of paths:**
 - Creation of participatory inventory, digital management tool and online map
 - Creation of different means of representation of this cultural heritage: sensitive discovery map of the area, survey books

- **Activation of a heritage community around the heritage of the pathways:**
 - Creation of different sectorial working groups: agriculture, tourism, rural paths....
 - Co-creation of participatory methods to work with the heritage: volunteer landscape and heritage workcamps, cultural walks...

- **An integrated approach to territorial entrepreneurship:**
 - Creation of a new flagship cultural route, the Tour du Morvan des Sommets
 - Promotion of the destination and the new routes: production of tourism packages, a brochure and of a website dedicated to the new tourist destination
 - The members of the agriculture working group have created an association accredited as a Groupement d'intérêt économique et Environnemental (GIEE), a Ministry of Agriculture label

3. Outcomes:

- The Tour du Morvan des Sommets serves as a catalyst for landscape initiatives and is a means of federating economic activities
- Boosted attractiveness of the territory through new narratives strengthening local identity and attracting new visitors
- Project of homologation of the new cultural route by the French national hiking federation for increased visibility and notoriety
- Development of a new destination website to promote narratives of the ecological transition and local involvement in tourism
- The GSF landscape maintenance actions showcase local sustainability practices and know-how and it works towards to strengthening the inhabitants' attachment to shared values and to raise the awareness of the challenges of climate change

The main achievement in terms of cultural tourism offer has been the launch of a new cultural route: [The Tour du Morvan des Sommets hiking itinerary](#), a 140 km

long circular path linking the 12 villages of the area. Elaborated through a bottom-up collaborative design, this is a new sustainable tourist destination in Morvan. The new website of the destination and a promotional brochure will be launched at the end of May 2024. They will foster the creation of new narratives by telling a story of a rural territory where the local inhabitants are actors of the ecological transition and where tourism is seen as a tool to maintain the territorial Commons.

The new routes are being promoted by the tourism offices of the territory (leaflets and website), which also promote and sell packages including the route(s).

With regards to the communities involved, after increasing awareness of the common cultural heritage in the form of the network of pathways, the heritage communities were activated through participative methodologies using the framework of the GSF landscape approach.

In this development of an integrated approach to territorial entrepreneurship tourism was used as a tool for recognising and diversifying economic activities based on the resources of a shared landscape. This resulted in a number of sectorial working groups (Agriculture, tourism, Art and territory) that led to the creation of a producer's association that has been certified as an Economic and Environmental Interest Group, a label of the French Ministry of Agriculture.

The idea of creating synergies between different economic sectors is an innovative approach. By breaking down the traditional silos between these sectors and promoting multi-skilled professional profiles, you can create a more resilient and adaptable local economy.

The INCULTUM pilot project has thus contributed to increasing the awareness of the shared cultural heritage, which, in turn, has led to the activation of a Heritage Community of the rural paths, and now hundreds of people gather to take part in the activities of the Rural Paths and Tourism working groups (WG). Those sectorial WGs coordinated by the INCULTUM project manager at Bibracte bring together around thirty elected representatives, citizens and socio-professionals.

To bring these heritage communities to life (activation), Bibracte and its partners have been successfully experimenting with the [Art and Territory](#) approach since 2021: themed visits, artists-in-residence, conferences, heritage summer workshops have been organised with the aim of mobilising players from a wide variety of backgrounds around the territorial Commons (primarily focused on the network of pathways). This collaborative approach led to the design of the first new cultural route, the *Tour du Morvan des Sommets*, mentioned above.

More news about this pilot: <https://incultum.eu/pilots/6-bibracte-morvan-ancient-paths-into-the-future/>

4. Further perspectives, difficulties, and challenges

- The attractiveness of the territory/destination has been boosted firstly by creating new narratives strengthening the identity of the local communities and, secondly, by attracting more and new types of visitors improving the destination brand. The itinerary has been selected by the two associations representing the French hiking federation to enter a national approval process for the route as a "Sentier de grande randonnée de Pays" (label GR de Pays). In March 2024, the project has been approved by the executive committee of the Morvan Regional National Park in and the assembly of mayors of the 12 communes of the Grand site de France. The project partners: the hiking federations, Bibracte and the Morvan Regional Nature Park will sign a partnership agreement in 2024 to implement the national certification process.

Labelling the new cultural route as «GR de pays» by the French national hiking federation, might take 3 to 4 years, this will give visibility and notoriety to the new destination, but the process will require major investment and long-term project engineering. As of 2025, the Bibracte museum will open in winter, which is why there is a need to extend the cultural and tourist offer and to develop the service provision. We plan to organize a winter sport event on the Tour du Morvan des Sommets to boost the new seasonality of the offer. The partners will need to find the necessary funding to bring these projects to fruition.

- The Grand Site de France landscape maintenance actions showcase local sustainability practices and know-how and, at the same time, it works towards to strengthening the inhabitants' attachment to shared values and to raise the awareness of the challenges of climate change and the need for sustainable agricultural practices.

The involvement of the local elected representatives and the emergence of a heritage community prove that the landscape approach is an effective tool for designing sustainable projects and strengthening democratic debate as part of the ecological and social transition in rural areas. Debates on the management plan, even when there is disagreement, is a way to empower the elected representatives and the inhabitants in the management of their heritage / territorial commons and show that they can have a concrete impact on their landscape.

The new cultural routes now serve as a catalyst for other landscape initiatives and as an inspiration in terms of method in the way it has succeeded in

federating economic, social and cultural activities based on shared landscape resources.

Besides, the rural path inventory tool and methodology is now being used in other territories of Morvan.

Identifying resource people in the local ecosystem and relying on their ability to pass on knowledge, with the development of their expertise will be a key factor for success.

- The programme of cultural events organised as part of the pilot project help to create social links and foster solidarity among the locals. The pilot plans to organize in the coming months an annual festival “the art of making your way” on the rural paths that will help institutionalize the common heritage in the local cultural policy. Our partner, the association Chemins is in the process of changing its governance to include the 12 villages of the territory in order to empower the elected representatives and local inhabitants in the production of the cultural program around the common heritage. One of the challenges over the coming months will be to find the necessary funding for the cultural events programme.
- The Agriculture WG that was set up in 2021 and represents the diversity of agricultural models present in the area has created a producer’s association that is in the process of being certified as an Economic and Environmental Interest Group (GIEE), a French Ministry of Agriculture label designed to promote the organisation of actors in the agricultural sector around collective sustainable projects. One of the goals is to diversify the famers’ activities to cater for slow tourism and improve the service provision. One of the challenges for the association will be to find a sustainable economic model based on the cooperative economy.
- From a more general perspective, the methodology of the pilot is now inspiring another project led by Bibracte and its partners around the water as a Common (project COUDRIER). Besides, Bibracte has been selected in new EU calls to ensure the continuity of the actions implemented with INCULTUM: Secretour (Horizon Europe) + EIP-agriculture and EIP forestry.

Pilot #7: Aaos, the shared river. Aaos/Vjosa valley (Greece-THM)⁷

1. The objectives achieved during the project, with emphasis on the innovative elements in each area.

The Greek pilot "Aaos the Shared River" effectively achieved the following objectives through innovative elements in various areas, focusing on enhancing cultural and natural heritage to promote sustainable and innovative cultural tourism.

1. Technological and Organizational Innovation:

- **Creation of a Knowledge Geobase and Business Intelligence (BI) Tools:** The project developed a digital infrastructure that integrated business intelligence tools with a comprehensive knowledge geobase. This system enabled the analysis, synthesis, and visualization of the region's physical, cultural, and socio-economic data. Such innovation supported decision-making processes and helped stakeholders understand the area's unique characteristics, enhancing strategic planning for cultural tourism.
- **Integrated Development Planning Support System (IDPSS):** Utilizing Integrated Development methodologies and systems such as IDPSS, stakeholders were able to extract and formulate specific actions for developing cultural tourism. This system combined interdisciplinary research with spatial decision-making systems to create a robust framework for understanding and addressing the needs of the region.

2. Community Empowerment and Participatory Development:

- **Empowering Local Communities:** The project engaged local communities in the planning and implementation of development actions. By involving locals in the research process and decision-making, the project ensured that the initiatives were grounded in the actual needs and preferences of the community, fostering a sense of ownership and responsibility.
- **Participatory Process for Cultural Route Development:** An innovative participatory process was utilized to open a new cultural route in Kallithea village. This initiative not only connected the village with significant local sites but also involved visitors and locals in collaborative activities, enhancing community bonds and promoting local culture. Through this initiative new types of tourism like voluntary tourism were introduced to solve specific problems and leverage cultural tourism in the area.

3. Promotion of Cultural Tourism and Products:

- **Website for Cultural Promotion:** A significant outcome was the creation of a website designed to promote the local culture to a broader audience outside Greece. This platform allows local stakeholders to offer cultural experiences,

⁷ THM's team: Sotiris Tsoukarelis and Thaleia Pantoula

facilitating direct interactions between the community and tourists, bypassing traditional intermediaries.

- **Innovative Cultural Products through P2P and Social Economy Models:** The project leveraged peer-to-peer production and social economy business models to promote innovative cultural products and services. This approach enabled the sustainable generation of income and job opportunities within the community, highlighting the social and economic benefits of integrating innovative business models in cultural tourism.

4. Sustainable Use of Natural Resources:

- **Environmental Monitoring and Education Initiatives:** The project addressed environmental sustainability by implementing initiatives for the monitoring and educational use of natural resources, like the Dragon Lake of Tymfi. Using open technologies and collaborative efforts, the project demonstrated how local communities could engage in responsible tourism while preserving their environmental heritage. Using the Design Global Manufacture Local model the pilot manufactured locally, tools that can be used to boost scientific tourism and monitor local environments.

2. The main products achieved in the project.

- The pilot's first product is a website⁸ with a social economy business model that presents insights of the culture of the area, offers a calendar of the local cultural events and gives the opportunity to local stakeholders to create and offer online cultural community based products/experiences. Already, more than six cultural experiences/products are offered by local stakeholders and more than 25 events are presented in the cultural calendar of the area.
- Another product created during the pilot is an Interactive Dashboard⁹ (which its data are also available in [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#)), a BI tool that gives citizens, local authorities and stakeholders the chance to convincingly establish the relationship between local development and cultural tourism, through data analysis and statistics, including socio-economic measures. Citizens, local authorities, visitors and stakeholders can monitor the area combine resources and data driven clues in order to propose their own evidence-based development actions and policies.
- The third product is an environment monitoring tool (waterjet)¹⁰ that was manufactured locally using the infrastructure of the local public library, taking advantage of open designs and cooperating with local social economy stakeholders and international academic partners. The tool is available for scientists who visit the area to use and for locals to monitor their fragile ecosystems.

⁸ <https://culturaltourism.gr/>

⁹ <https://public.tableau.com/app/profile/social.analytics.gr/viz/GreeceAoosthesharedriver/Intro>

¹⁰ <https://newdexterity.org/autoboat/>

- The last product developed in the pilot are the two cultural routes. The first one connects, through a path in the woods, the village of Kalithea with the monument chapel of St Constantine, passing by three local businesses. The path was opened collaboratively from visitors along with locals, introducing volunteer tourism in the area. It is published on a digital platform¹¹ for visitors to follow and also in [Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#). The second is a transhumance route¹² that connects the [Vlach villages of Aetomilitsa and Gramos with the upper Vjosa valley](#) and the path created from INCULTUM's Albanian partners. Combined, they make a transborder route based on Vlachs and their nomadic culture.

3. Difficulties and challenges encountered during these years of the project.

Throughout the years of the INCULTUM project, the Greek pilot faced significant challenges that stemmed not only from project-related complexities but also from the socio-economic conditions of the area. Konitsa is characterized by economic hardships, a declining and aging population, and a lack of robust public infrastructure. These factors posed additional hurdles in implementing a project aimed at revitalizing the region through cultural tourism. Despite these challenges, the project managed to make a substantial positive impact:

1. **Stakeholder Coordination:** One of the key challenges encountered involved coordinating diverse stakeholders involved in the project. Managing relationships with various local actors such as cultural associations, groups of interest, local administrations, and business associations required substantial time and a deep understanding of their distinct interests and needs. The THM's team invested considerable effort in building trust and collaboration among local businesses, cultural associations, and administrative bodies, fostering a community-driven approach to tourism development.
2. **Cultural and Environmental Sensitivities:** In a region with significant natural and cultural heritage but limited resources to manage and promote these assets, the project faced the dual challenge of boosting tourism while preserving its pristine environments and traditions. Strategic planning and sensitive implementation were crucial in achieving this balance, ensuring that tourism development did not compromise the area's cultural integrity or environmental sustainability.
3. **Data Collection and Analysis:** The depopulation and aging demographic made engaging with local communities for data collection a challenging task. The project adapted by employing both innovative and traditional methods (qualitative and quantitative empirical research) to gather accurate

¹¹ <https://www.wikiloc.com/hiking-trails/cultural-route-in-kallithea-by-the-high-mountains-incultum-116151825>

¹² <https://www.wikiloc.com/hiking-trails/vlachs-transhumance-path-grammos-by-the-high-mountains-incultum-140975712>

and comprehensive data. Particularly in engaging cultural associations and visitors effectively, the project required meticulous planning and execution to ensure accuracy and relevance, thereby enhancing the understanding of the area's potential and needs.

4. **Technological Integration:** Implementing advanced technologies and business intelligence tools for cultural tourism development presented difficulties, especially in terms of tailoring these technologies to meet local specificities and ensuring they added value to the stakeholders. The project successfully implemented these tools tailored to the local context, providing stakeholders with valuable insights to drive informed decisions for sustainable development.
5. **Socio-Economic Barriers:** Addressing the economic scarcity and infrastructural deficits, the project not only aimed to attract tourists but also to empower and equip the local population with skills and tools necessary for sustainable development.

Despite these challenges, the Greek Pilot demonstrated remarkable resilience and adaptability. These challenges were met with strategic responses, including adopting flexible project management approaches, enhancing stakeholder engagement strategies, and leveraging innovative technologies to foster sustainable cultural tourism in Konitsa. The experience and lessons learned from overcoming these difficulties have contributed significantly to the project's resilience and success.

4. How INCULTUM's action will improve the study areas.

The improvements initiated by INCULTUM project through the pilot "Aos the Shared River" in Konitsa are set to provide enduring benefits and foster sustainable development in the area. Here's how the project's contributions are set to evolve and continue impacting the study area positively to ensure long-term benefits for the region:

Sustainable Tourism Growth

The foundation laid by INCULTUM's pilot by developing an interactive map and a dynamic digital presence for Konitsa's cultural and natural resources has paved the way for a sustainable tourism model. These tools not only make the region's heritage accessible but also promote an educational approach to tourism. This is expected to attract a more responsible visitor demographic, interested in authentic experiences that respect the local environment and culture, thereby fostering a sustainable economic cycle that benefits the entire community economy while preserving the area's unique heritage.

Enhanced Community Engagement and Empowerment

One of the most impactful outcomes of the Greek pilot is the empowerment of the local community through participatory planning and capacity-building workshops. The pilot's participatory approach has strengthened community

cohesion and engagement. As local stakeholders continue to be involved in decision-making and development processes, their capacity to influence and sustain local development initiatives increases. This empowerment fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility towards local heritage and tourism development and creates a robust framework for self-sustained growth.

Capacity Building and Skill Development

The workshops and training sessions conducted as part of the project have equipped residents with new skills and knowledge, particularly in areas like digital marketing, cultural heritage management, and sustainable tourism practices, ensuring they can effectively contribute to and benefit from the growing tourism sector. These capabilities will enable the community to manage and promote their cultural assets more effectively, ensuring long-term benefits.

Policy Development and Strategic Planning

The strategic frameworks and policy recommendations developed through INCULTUM are instrumental in guiding future cultural tourism strategies. These policies are likely to encourage more coordinated efforts between government bodies, non-profits, the private sector and community organizations to invest in and promote cultural tourism in a way that respects and enhances local traditions and environments. This strategic approach ensures that development efforts are inclusive and aligned with the region's long-term goals.

Robust Networks and Collaborative Opportunities

The Greek pilot has successfully established a network among local actors, regional partners, and international partners, fostering collaboration that extends beyond the project's duration. These networks are crucial for future project developments, providing avenues for knowledge exchange, additional funding opportunities, and exchanges of best practices that can further enhance the cultural and economic vitality of Konitsa. Such collaborations are likely to spawn new initiatives that will continue to promote and develop Konitsa's cultural and natural assets.

Cultural Revitalization and Innovative Use of Technology

Through active promotion, revitalization and documentation of local cultural events, traditions, and historical sites Aoo the Shared River pilot has set the stage for an ongoing cultural renaissance in Konitsa by attracting cultural tourism and educational interest. This not only supports the local economy but also ensures that cultural heritage is passed down to future generations, maintaining its relevance and vibrancy. The continued focus on cultural education and engagement not only boosts tourism but also ensures that these traditions are preserved and celebrated.

Moreover, the use of innovative technology such as interactive maps and social media promotion sets a precedent for continued technological integration in the area. This can lead to more innovative approaches to marketing, visitor engagement, and cultural preservation in the future and introduces a modern

element to traditional practices, making them more appealing and accessible to a global audience.

Technological Integration and Visitor Engagement

The project's use of advanced digital tools to enhance visitor experience and engagement sets a precedent for the future integration of technology in cultural tourism. This approach helps in crafting detailed visitor profiles, tailoring experiences that meet specific interests, and effectively managing the impact of tourism on local resources. Continued technological innovation will keep Konitsa at the forefront of sustainable tourism practices.

These forward-looking initiatives spearheaded by INCULTUM's pilot are poised to transform Konitsa into a model of sustainable cultural tourism, where economic development and cultural preservation go hand in hand. As the community continues to build on these foundations, the project ensures that the benefits of tourism development are both far-reaching and long-lasting, thereby enhancing the quality of life for residents and enriching the experience for visitors.

5. Description of the scientific or industrial (in the case of SMEs) breakthrough developed during the project. Please indicate if in any case a prototype (app, or similar) has been created that could generate economic benefit.

The four products developed in the pilot "Aaos the Shared River" can generate economic benefit.

- First, the website was developed within a social economy business framework. It can generate economic benefit based on a "non for profit" philosophy. This means that it can generate more benefit for local societies offering community based cultural experiences/products in the platform, and at the same time it can be operated by The High Mountains Social Cooperative Enterprise sustainably. This "portfolio" of community based experiences/products can give back the majority of the economic benefit it creates to local communities for the development of community projects. The benefit for The High Mountains SCE will be to sustain the digital infrastructure, grow its content and create more jobs, according to its constitutional purposes.
- The interactive dashboard is an evidence-based development planning tool. The High Mountains SCE will replicate it to other areas, and it can continue generating economic benefit as a service to local and regional authorities, planers, and development agencies.
- The third product developed, the waterjet, can be rented to researchers who want to conduct their research on the water resources of the area. But it generates economic benefit in many more ways. The

waterjet was manufactured with local infrastructure, and it can be fixed, replicated, and upgraded locally. The global knowledge used is now common local knowledge and could lead to the development of more open-source projects. In parallel, its use in monitoring the local water ecosystems can help in sustaining the generation of economic benefit from the well-preserved natural environment. The Design Global Manufacture Local model can be a sustainable way of generating local economic value in remote areas.

- Finally, the two cultural routes created and uploaded to international hiking platforms will continue to bring visitors to explore the area and its culture years after INCULTUM project generating economic benefits for the area and its people.

Pilot #8: Vjosa, the shared river. Vjosa/Aoos valley (Albania-CER)¹³

1. Main objectives of the pilot:

The INCULTUM pilot in the Vjosa valley, SE Albania, focused particularly on the tangible and intangible heritage of the Vlachs, aiming at recording, preserving and promoting the currently endangered heritage values of this community. The Vlachs who are known to themselves as *Arāmān/Rāmān*, are a cultural and ethnolinguistic group that have historically inhabited swathes of the Balkans territory. They are distinguished by their language, which is a dialect derived from Latin, and by their ways of living, which are primarily based on long-distance seasonal pastoral transhumance. In Albania, the Vlachs are considered a national minority and are acknowledged as such according to the national legal framework.¹⁴

The Vlachs have suffered a long historical discrimination and intimidation, which has consequently hampered the preservation and appreciation of the symbolic aspects of their culture, including their past traditions, customs, rituals and material culture. Therefore, the pilot action employed a ground-up approach to recreate aspects of Vlachs past, and generate past narratives that evolves around their historic transhumant routes and the livelihood aspects, including the construction of an authentic dwelling.

2. Main achievements/products:

a) Revitalization of historical transhumant routes:

The Upper Vjosa valley was one of the main routes used during Vlach seasonal nomadic movements from winter pastures in the Ionian coast, towards the summer pastures in the mountain areas of southeast Albania. Very often, small

¹³ CeRPHAAL's team: Eglja Serjani and Ardit Miti

¹⁴ Law number 96/2017, article 3, point 2, For the protection of national minorities in the Republic of Albania.

groups of Vlach families built their seasonal summer encampment in the mountainous areas of the Vjosa valley. These movements are only preserved on the memories of those Vlach individuals that once were part of a nomadic society. Therefore, an ethnoarchaeological survey was primarily conducted aiding at recording and mapping past itineraries. Subsequently, these historic itineraries were surveyed by project team members and young local volunteers and recorded using GNSS. The trails were presented as digital online maps, allowing exploration of an historical and natural landscape, consisting of sites, monuments, traditional villages, meadows, forests, and etc.¹⁵ The routes pass through marginalised areas that are not often benefited by tourism, therefore in addition to promoting the surrounding cultural and natural landscape it may provide economic benefits to the local communities. Both cultural routes and the digital online maps are available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community:

- [Walking with the Vlach: Hikes in the mountains of the Upper Vjosa valley](#)
- [Walking with the Vlachs: Hiking trail from the village of Draçova up to the Mount Nemërçka](#)

b) Construction of a Vlach dwelling site

The Vlach have endured a challenging historical journey that did not help for the survival of any standing physical object as representative of their history. Therefore, we relied on the surviving memories of the last generation of Vlachs, who lived a transhumant way of life to materialize and reconstruct the lost symbolic aspect of their past by constructing a traditional dwelling known as *kalive*. It represents a simple circular structure build of wood and covered with a thatched roof. The walls and floors are mud-plastered, and the interior contains a simple hearth and wooden shelves. The interior of the hut is arranged as a museum displaying old furniture and tools that are used by Vlachs in the past. The dwelling is located on the outskirts of the town of Përmet, within the territory of a camping site frequented by visitors, allowing it to become better known. This location corresponds to one of the Vlach's temporary daily camps used during their seasonal transhumant movements between summer and winter pastures. The construction process involved elderly Vlachs, researchers, students, and volunteers, enabling the preservation and transfer of past master techniques to the new generation. Additionally, an interpretation panel was designed, providing a brief history of the Vlachs along with a map showcasing their main transhumance routes. There are QR code generators highlighted on the touristic panel offering quick access to an online map on *wikiloc*.

¹⁵ <https://www.wikiloc.com/hiking-trails/vlachs-transhumance-route-108659966>;
<https://www.wikiloc.com/hiking-trails/walking-with-the-vlachs-hiking-trail-from-the-village-of-dracova-up-to-the-mount-nemercka-135792697>

For selected picture see:

<https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/reconstruction-of-vlachs-dwelling/>

3. Foster awareness, understanding and appreciation of Vlach minority culture:

In addition to preserving and promoting Vlach culture, an important aim of the project team in the Vjosa valley was to activate appreciation and understanding among local communities about the Vlach history. This can subsequently aid to pave the way towards the future institutionalization and long-lasting sustainability of this minority heritage. These initiatives included a number of local encounters designed to establish familiarisation to this undervalued culture, creating local synergy and fostering a sense of solidarity among the community. The meetings successfully brought together Vlachs, other community members, heritage specialists, researchers, students, local stakeholders, and visitors, stimulating effective discussions about the future of Vlach heritage. These gatherings also facilitated a mutual learning process; while on the one hand they provided living stories and insights about Vlachs traditions, the involvement of the researches on the other side, offered for the Vlachs the opportunity to rediscover a new historical narrative of their past that ultimately stimulated awareness and self-appreciation for their history.

Further, in collaboration with the Municipality of Përmet and other local stakeholders, CeRPHAAL established a new festive event dedicated to the Vlach culture - called the *Vlach Open Days*. During this event, a number of dynamic cross-cultural activities were organized, showcasing aspects related to their past life, such as the traditional wool processing and weaving which were demonstrated by Vlach women at the *kalive* dwelling site. Additionally, a digital photo documentary that is the result of extensive archival work, was presented under the title '*The Vlachs: a short history as seen through the lens of photography*'. This was complemented by a film documentary featuring key moments in the history of the Vlachs in Albania prior to the 1970s. The success of this initiative led to its recognition as an annual festival to be organized by the Municipality of Përmet and supported by CeRPHAAL during its initial years.

For selected picture see: <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/vlachs-open-days/>

Training session for mutual learning:

The pilot project in the Vjosa valley organized a series of training activities aiming at disseminating knowledge about the cultural heritage landscape and discussing current challenges related to the management of the tourism sector in the region. The target groups for these meetings included local tourism specialist, tour guides, stakeholders, and students. Some sections of the training focused on the Vlach minority heritage, emphasising its importance as an

integral part of the area's cultural tourism assets. Additionally, CeRPHAAL provided guided field training tours dedicated to the local tour guides and heritage specialists in the municipality, offering essential information about the history of the town, the notable landmarks, and the historical and environmental landscape of the area.

For selected picture see: <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/incultum-albania-training-session/>

Promotion and dissemination tools

Another important aim of the pilot team in the Vjosa valley was to highlight and promote the diversity of cultural heritage resources embodied in the mountainous landscape of the region.

In alignment with this goal, tour packages and brochures were designed for single or combined sites, monuments, and aeras. One brochure was dedicated to introducing, for the first time to the public, some of the area's overlooked and neglected heritage. This includes the currently endangered military heritage from the Second World War and the Communist Period. Another informative brochure focused on the Vlachs and their historical connection to the territory of the Vjosa valley. This latter brochure presents the newly designed nomadic routes, along with other cultural landmarks found along these historical pathways.

These materials are accompanied by easy-to-read maps, brief explanatory texts, and images, as well as QR codes that provide links to digital maps. Special attention was also given to presenting and introducing these promotional materials to heritage specialists and other tourism stakeholders in the pilot area.

For selected pictures see: <https://www.digitalmeetsculture.net/article/new-visitors-leaflets-launched-in-the-pilot-area-of-the-upper-vjosa-valley/>

Pilot #9: Historic Graves (Ireland-EACHTRA)¹⁶

For ten years before INCULTUM, we had worked with over 500 Irish community groups and published over 600 historic graveyard surveys online (www.historicgraves.com) evolving to a Creative Commons sharing/ownership model whereby the resulting digital datasets are co-owned with the local community groups and the project funders, such as local authorities and Local Action Groups. Through the INCULTUM Project we were tasked with extending the tourism relevance of our web platform and our established community of online

¹⁶ Eachtra Director: John Tierney (john@historicgraves.com). Project Team: Maurizio Toscano, Choryna Kiely, Martha Hannon and Dónal O'Tiarnaigh

partners. While the project started in 2010 as a community archaeology project its tourism relevance is based on genealogical tourism.

INCULTUM allowed us to test several ideas we had been nurturing since 2010 and also develop some innovative approaches based on the synergies from our cooperations with the other INCULTUM partners.

In summary, as an SME, we were particularly stimulated by the High Mountains (Pilot #7) approach to combining large digital datasets for tourism management at a local level as well as the Uppsala University (Pilot #10) approach to measuring and mapping tourists' interactions with key places. Later in the project, the pilot's dealing with diverting visitors from overtourism locations such as the Algarve (Pilot #2) were stimulating to us as they raise issues of how to pitch the level of communication for cultural tourism especially in the context of the social class of visitors.

As field archaeologists, we did not have experience in gathering user feedback but both the (WP7) and SDU (WP3) approaches to measuring and communicating with the broader public surprised us by helping us realise one of our key opportunities was hiding in plain sight. For ten years we have focused on grassroots community surveys and conversations under our Learn By Doing approach and only rarely did we ask for formal feedback. The INCULTUM methodology of [using questionnaires](#) proved very fruitful for us and has now become a key tool which we use regularly and allows us to communicate with over 11,000 of our online members.

There were also philosophical and strategic approaches used by the other pilots which we found very suited to our work and our partner groups - the Bibracte (pilot#6) approach to Commons and Territorial Landscape are not common discussions we encounter in Ireland, yet, we found them matching with practices we regularly encounter eg. local communities put cultural identity to the fore. The strong sense of place that survives in rural Ireland fits very well with the Territories' thinking. The UGR approach of payment-for-services (pilot #1) we believe could suit the Irish situation whereby local authorities are the stewards of many heritage sites but do not have the facilities for regular care and maintenance and local volunteers are often willing to assist in actions such as grasscutting and strimming on seemingly neglected heritage sites

We tested hypotheses relating to livestreaming for tourism engagement, dark tourism for marketing local heritage projects, and different types of trails/micro-trails including a new Destinations element built into our web platform. We also innovated an AI solution to a data entry problem which developed during the project due to COVID-19 impacts.

Figure 4. A7 brochure with dynamic QR

Surprisingly, we feel our strongest result, inspired in association with some local groups, involving simple printed and digital A7 brochures with built-in dynamic QR codes, with the benefits of a network effect, can result in local communities becoming partners in large tourist intelligence dataset projects.

The combination of [visitor questionnaires](#) and visitor behaviour tracking are simple tools to put local communities to the fore with their local authority/local action group partners, in the management of the tourism resource. With the right design, local resident satisfaction can be monitored along with visitor satisfaction, thereby following the INCULTUM philosophy of using tourism as a tool to protect and support local communities and their cultural heritage.

Livestreaming the Past

We had high hopes for this element of the project. By 'livestreaming the past' we mean bringing an audience to places of rich cultural heritage, many of which are of historic significance, and by visiting the place, one was, in a way, visiting the past. Online gamers and YouTube communities have innovated studio/home-based livestream media production to a high standard. In Real Life (IRL) livestreaming was developing in 2018/2019¹⁷ and we wished to test its utility for building audiences for local heritage. The attraction of IRL livestreaming is that it did not require substantial post-filming editing work while the live element could be used to build a sense of involvement and immediacy in how the communities could interact with, and build, an audience.

We tested the hypothesis using a number of approaches resulting in a YouTube playlist¹⁸ with approximately 30 videos being produced. We tested this approach with communities in Ballyhoura and Duhallow, Limerick and Cork.

1. Smartphone with gimbal

Several software options were examined and we settled on two approaches. Firstly, Prism for iOS proved to be good for live streaming from the field as it allowed annotations to be drawn live on the screen. It also allowed logos to be shown which is important for branding.

¹⁷ <https://dl.acm.org/doi/abs/10.1145/3290605.3300459>

¹⁸ <https://qrco.de/bevjKJ>

YouTube Live was a good solution also but for much of the INCULTUM period it was stronger on Android rather than iOS. It evolved in time to allow two different users to meet live on the screen while traversing a site and tests for this approach were promising. However, the technology did not mature until early 2024 which was not especially useful for INCULTUM but shows the trend is towards improvement.

2. Feiyu Pocket and Pocket 2S connected to smartphone.

We are still using these two cameras for field recording but they failed at the IRL livestreaming from the beginning. Their built-in connections to YouTube and Facebook Live were never robust and were frustrating for us to test, so much so that we never brought this solution to test with local groups.

Ultimately, livestreaming did not work because 4G networks are not sufficiently established in the remote places where we work and where our community partners are based. Livestreams become laggy and even drop their connections - making the viewing experience suboptimal. In the end, following much internal debate, we settled on a hybrid approach. We recorded site visits 'as if' we were live streaming and practiced as if we were giving live tours to an audience who were standing there with us. This approach did work for us as heritage professionals but when we tested it with community groups there were issues with confidence, privacy and practice. The method we developed we called "No Edit" video tours and it has potential for future use but it was too difficult to expand out to community groups.

Dark Tourism

Allied with the livestreaming was the Dark Tourism hypothesis testing. We wanted to test the hypothesis that taking an explicitly dark tourism approach to local history storytelling would result in larger audiences for our communities. We intended to video much of the dark tourism approach. The key dark tourism story we focused on was stories related to the 1845-52 Great Irish Famine. Every parish in Ireland has Famine-related stories and we aimed to focus on these stories but with rigour and a scientific approach because contentious political stories need scientific underpinnings.

Using drone-based Structure from Motion we surveyed some Famine related cemeteries and developed methods for identifying unmarked graves of various types. Combining photogrammetry and LiDAR we identified a new typology of Irish institutional mass/common graves. Academically, this was very satisfying to our team of field archaeologists and it fits well with current politically sensitive issues

relating to a number of cases of disputed burial practices from the mid-19th to mid-20th century institutions, such as Workhouses and Mother and Baby Homes.

Fieldwork using remote sensing was done in Mayo, West Cork and South Cork as well as in West Waterford and mid-Laois. New cholera epidemic graves were identified along with the new typology of narrow and long graves associated with mass or common (non-family related) graves. This Dark Tourism marketing approach evolved into an academic study. We presented three different but related talks relating to dark tourism and Irish institutional burial practices to three conferences in 2023: the IAI in Cork in April, the EAA conference in Belfast in August, and the TCD Dead Body conference in September.

This work is continuing beyond INCULTUM with funding being sought for a further season of fieldwork in June 2024 with final results being presented to a mass graves session in EAA in Rome in August 2024. The Dark Tourism approach was tested in Ballyhoura and Achill with many other smaller interactions taking place elsewhere.

COVID, Data Entry and TextHarvester

From the start, COVID-19 affected our project. As our workshops are mostly outdoors, we did see an increase in attendance during Covid by older community members who “wanted to get out of the house but in safe conditions” and anecdotally our average age cohort changed from the mid-60s to early 70s. Fieldwork continued well but the online data inputting, which normally was undertaken by local community groups, began to fail. The older cohort attending the training was less capable of data entry, with a few exceptions. As a result, our team, and one of our clients (Ballyhoura CLG) took on increased responsibility for data entry which was not ideal as it was not costed for, nor had we the personnel always available.

We tested several solutions to this problem. Firstly, we tried to record less data ie. fewer data points for each gravestone. That was not ideal and we regretted this decision within months of starting. Then we tried to leverage the text recognition capabilities in iOS to copy text directly from the survey photographs. This worked well with late 20th century headstones with good colour contrast between the gravestone and the painted inscriptions, however using an iPhone for this in the field was too problematic for our community groups so it failed our internal testing whereby all the survey works should be ‘doable’ by non-professionals.

Ultimately, the solution was found in AI and the LLM ChatGPT. We invested some time in using ChatGPT 3.5 to develop prompts and scripts for good-quality handwriting recognition of the original field record sheets. In late spring 2023 we

were happy with the 75% accuracy of the process and then in late Summer, with the launch of ChatGPT 4, the quality of the transcriptions jumped to 85-95%.

The software to run this was published on GitHub and is called TextHarvester¹⁹. One simply uploads a jpg or multiple record sheets as a pdf to the TextHarvester software, present a number of localised prompts relating to common surnames and placenames, and the software parses the handwritten sheets to digital spreadsheets structured as database records and fields. We tested this approach with students in a post-leaving certificate course in Cork City (Cultural and Heritage Studies at Cork College of FET, Tramore Road Campus) from 2022-2024 and were satisfied this approach is of good enough quality to be used in our field surveys from now on.

Instead of the communities typing the data in - they take the task of checking the quality of the transcriptions before they are published. A week's work is now projected to be reduced to a day for every data batch.

Destinations, Trails, Micro-Trails and Tourism Intelligence

For the first time, we added an explicitly touristic element to our web platform (www.historicgraves.com/destination/ballyhoura). Before this, we knew the web platform was a tourist resource and a Project module had been added to the platform but it did not appeal to our funding partners - many agreed to use the project approach but it seemed to suit our archaeologists way of thinking rather than our partners' requirements. Destinations allowed us to define a local area and present the archaeological and genealogical data we had gathered as a series of stories, surveys and online trails. The online trail we tested is a StoryMap²⁰ which is relatively simple to use but much of our time was aimed at defining the scope of each trail to make it easier for community groups to use. The Destinations module has strong potential for genealogical tourism and we propose to develop the product in coming years. Research on the Destinations module was done with community partners in Achill, Co. Mayo as well as Kilfinnane and Charleville, Co. Limerick and Co. Cork.

Following an INCULTUM team meeting in April 2023 our approach to micro-trails began to change. Observing the methods used by the Uppsala team (Pilot #10) for measuring visitor actions and experiences, we were inclined to extend their approach to Ireland albeit using different technology.

¹⁹ <https://qrco.de/bevjj>

²⁰ <https://storymap.knightlab.com/>

Many interactions with partner groups throughout Ireland had attempted to design graveyard micro-trails but we were not satisfied with the solutions emerging until July 2023, in particular following discussions with an experienced local heritage group in Quin, Co. Clare.

This was late in the INCULTUM schedule but testing different designs and hypotheses finally got us to a product with which we are satisfied. Our original intention was to design destination cultural routes of different scales, at a macro and micro level, thinking we could benefit local communities by increasing their visitor numbers. What emerged from the testing is a multilayered tourism tool based on the foundations of a locally researched and written trail but with greater capabilities than we originally intended.

We are calling the resulting micro-trail brochure *The Past in Your Pocket*. A7 in size and available as a printed or digital document, it is a clean and simple trail document which, allied with dynamic QR technology, becomes a powerful cultural tourism tool.

We learned about dynamic QR codes in publishing the site visitor surveys on nine sites. A single QR code (affixed to a sign on the graveyard gates) was presented to trigger a Google Forms questionnaire. An initial reluctance about the questionnaire itself was soon overcome when we were advised the length of the questionnaire would not affect the number of replies and that we should be happy with a 2-5% response rate. The key issue was to get the questionnaires out to the public so that our work package partners could gather the data required. In some graveyards, we received 10-20% reply rates which was strong but interestingly we realised the dynamic QR codes were also giving us anonymised information from people who clicked on the survey link but chose not to fill in the questionnaire.

We quickly realised that dynamic QR codes were a two-way communication tool. The visitor was presented with new a micro-trail and various information types (questionnaires, blog posts, 3D models, scientific reports, wikipedia pages) when they clicked the QR code but we also gleaned anonymised tourist intelligence including date and time of visit as well as country and often city/town of origin, based on browser settings.

We then expanded the QR codes onto the *Past in Your Pocket* brochures and now not only were we getting visitor intelligence from a QR code affixed to the graveyard gate but we were also getting intelligence from the site trail in printed and digital formats and also as site cards affixed alongside the point of origin in the heritage site. We made a [pop-up trail in one graveyard](#) (Ardmore, Co. Waterford) and after the INCULTUM test we counted nearly 400 people who clicked on the site

survey link - of whom 75 gave good-quality replies to the questionnaire (interestingly, half of our visitors were on day trips and were arriving at the site completely by chance). Most of the respondents had 3rd level education which perhaps explains their willingness to reply to the long detailed questionnaire. The pop-up micro-trail consisting of eight points of interest, each with a unique dynamic QR code, was then interacted with between 2500-2800 times. Providing us with anonymised visit information on date, time and country/city of origin.

Larger tourism businesses using dynamic QR codes must already be using them for business intelligence but we believe our approach now allows our project partners to participate in potential broad coalitions of data intelligence gathering and analysis.

On its own, the use of feedback questionnaires in our interpretative heritage literature was stimulating for our team. We now have a means to gather quantitative and qualitative feedback from users, residents and tourists. This has many potential usages including reporting maintenance issues, vandalism and littering. Primarily, we envisage the tool being used to put the local community at the forefront of cultural tourism engagements.

Conclusions

The significance of this development for us is that while our community partners have a right to own their heritage digital datasets we now see the situation emerging whereby they also have the right to own the tourism intelligence which can be gleaned through that same heritage data. Tourism data no longer needs to be the preserve of big business but grassroots entities, forming collaborations in sustainable and creative tourism, can bring more than intangible knowledge 'to the table'. Citizen science projects like ours, grassroots-based, can stake a claim to broader elements of the digital commons. Dynamic QR codes also bring our web platform data into the real world when we print and laminate individual headstone records, or stories and affix them to the object in the field. The same approach can be applied to any large cultural heritage datasets. Placenames, other genealogical datasets, folklore - all can be geolocated and used in a similar manner.

Overall the requirement for grassroots community groups to communicate with their cultural tourists, or in some cases to convert 'sun and sea' visitors into cultural tourists, has been stimulating. If the solution lies in the problem then it may be postulated that the solution to issues of overtourism entails both better resource management and better communication with all visitors. Clearer, simpler cultural tourism stories can be pitched at the mass tourism market as well as at the more niche cohort we currently address.

Pilot #10: Escape into the Archipelago landscape. Baltic ocean and the great lakes of Sweden (Sweden-UU)²¹

1. Objectives achieved

In the pilot, *Escape into the Archipelago Landscape*, the focus has been on innovative ways to understand visitors and their spatiotemporal behaviour and to integrate the insights in participatory workshops with local and regional stakeholders. With an amplified understanding of tourists' interests and behaviour patterns, the pilot contributes with an innovative mixed method to understand the spatiotemporal movements and the interactions that take place in the meeting between the visitors, the visited community, and the cultural heritage. Furthermore, these innovative methods, in terms of understanding tourists' behaviour and through a participatory approach, revealed both challenges and opportunities for the specific locations. Collecting data on spatiotemporal mobility has provided insights into consumption patterns and factors impacting tourist engagement, as well as the exposure of different areas.

Geocoded services have been developed to support the marketing of tourism in depopulated areas, such as:

- New methods and tools for segmenting tourists based on revealed behaviours;
- Creation of a digital repository for spatial and other data connected to the project ([Zenodo INCULTUM Community](#));
- Co-creation of knowledge related to policy and strategy formulation and integration in collaboration between local stakeholders, destination management and marketing organisations, and actors on regional levels.

2. The project contributes to INCULTUM through the following innovations:

#1. Understanding behaviours in a spatio-temporal context

By combining different data sets, common characteristics, needs, and behaviours among consumer groups are identified, contributing to insights on different consumption patterns that can facilitate destination management, planning of marketing activities, and distributing the flow of tourists within a destination. By combining four sets of data the UU team has developed a model for collecting mobility data among recreational visitors combined with background information and data on how individuals portray the destination; mobile phone data, GPS loggers, questionnaires, and netnography.

²¹ UU's team: Sabine Gebert Persson, Marina Toger, Anna-Carin Nordvall, John Östh and Mikael Gidhagen

2. Participatory design and involvement of the community

To facilitate the involvement of the community in an inclusive approach, a bottom-up process is developed building on the stakeholders' needs, challenges, and identification of opportunities.

A six-step model has been developed to derive the territorial touristic intelligence:

Part 1. Anchoring. Through interviews and conversations with different stakeholders in the respective destinations, the location-specific challenges and opportunities are identified. This is a continuous and iterative process based on dialogue with different stakeholders, such as the folklore societies, municipality/regional actors, hotels, and other actors. Based on the anchoring process, the data collection strategy is developed.

Part 2. Data collection - Existing movement patterns. Based on the dialogical communication, movement patterns through collected mobile data and GIS data along with surveys provide insights to identify the unexplored and potential places to develop, and the areas that run the risk of becoming congested if further exploited. The results are communicated continuously with DMOs. In these activities, the different stakeholders at the destinations have the opportunity to take an active part in the data collection and the result from the study on the tourists' movement patterns. All these surveys and GPS trajectories are available in our Zenodo INCULTUM Community:

- Survey of tourists in Öregrund 2021 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932299>
- GPS trajectories of tourists on Torsö and Brommö 2021 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932187>
- Survey of tourists in Österbybruk 2021 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932349>
- Survey of tourists on Torsö and Brommö 2021 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932147>
- Survey of tourists in Öregrund 2023 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10933143>
- Survey of tourists and website visits in Öregrund 2023 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932981>
- GPS trajectories of tourists in Öregrund 2022 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10931985>
- GPS trajectories of tourists in Öregrund 2023 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10928114>
- Survey of tourists on Gotland 2023 from INCULTUM Sweden Pilot: <https://zenodo.org/records/10932100>

Part 3. Movement patterns and perceptions - in this part, the researchers analyse mobile data together with the surveys, GIS data, and Netnography. This analysis has also been integrated into academic courses, where students play a part in identifying research questions and analysing the material. Through this process, iterative learning takes place while also allowing for new perspectives on the material.

Part 4. Workshops. Based on the results derived from the data analysis, workshops are arranged with the actors in the specific destination, in which data is presented and discussed in workshops with stakeholders. Service development and innovation processes are discussed. Through discussions, an idea-generation process is initiated based on the stakeholders' needs and the identified potential of the destination, integrating the results of the mixed method analysis in participatory workshops as a primer to start the discussion and continued collaboration between stakeholders. One of the participatory approaches used in the project builds on the idea of Geodesign (Steinitz 2012) to bridge conflicting interests, by using the results of GPS tracking heat maps as background for discussion about the location of services (e.g. tourist routes) and working towards decision and implementation.

Part 5. Newly developed ideas are turned into practice, such as in the form of new walking trails, new collaborations, or new processes.

Part 6. Training sessions where stakeholders are trained in using the mixed method approach to gain knowledge on movement patterns and perceptions.

3. Innovative practices

The project has among other things resulted in practices such as:

- Increasing the awareness of tourism activity off-season
- New or further developed Websites
- New collaborations
- Usage of different participatory approaches
- Training sessions for a variety of stakeholders

3. Difficulties and challenges

Difficulties

The pandemic had a fundamental effect on our study, and on all partners and visitors involved in tourism activities in the study areas, since we were unable to approach stakeholders and visitors in ways we had planned to. That being said, the pandemic instead offered an opportunity to study how unplanned

events/shocks affect tourism in rural areas, and we learned a lot from this. It was clear that rural tourism grew during the pandemic, and that our study areas gained in the number of visitors. However, as the pandemic was a reality as the INCULTUM project started, we were unable to establish a baseline for a normal season. In addition to the pandemic, the odd weather caused additional problems related to the study of tourist behaviour. During the study period, we experienced both record-level dry and warm summers, as well as the opposite, as the summer of 2023 had 600% of the normal precipitation in parts of our study areas. This affected visitors' choice of out-/indoor activities, and due to the above-indicated problem with establishing a baseline for "normal" behaviour, we found it difficult to describe a typical season. With the climate in mind, extreme or at least more variable weather may be the "new normal" of the future and for the tourism industry to cope with.

Challenges

At times we found it challenging to recruit responses. This was both due to the difficulties outlined above (the pandemic in particular) and also to the fact that rural destinations rarely have a natural point of entry/exit and that personal vehicles are the dominant transport mode. This means that it is uncertain if we at all times were able to recruit a representative sample for our studies. Since we had problems with establishing a baseline for the tourism activities (see the section on difficulties above) it is possible that we did not accurately identify locations with more or less visitors reflecting the identified difficulties.

4. How INCULTUM's action will improve the study areas

The actions of the INCULTUM Pilot 10 resulted in evidence of quadruple helix (e.g., Caryannis 2009) effects, through collaboration between academia, local authorities, business organisations and civic society/residents.

As a result of workshops and training sessions with local stakeholders, new walking trails have been developed, with respective focus on Nature, History and Family. In Öregrund, for example, the online actions also contributed to popularising the 'historical brass plaque' walk. These new trails and new ways of developing services will facilitate in distributing visitors over larger geographical areas, and in attracting new visitors.

The scientific methods and participatory models we used facilitated new ways and methods for understanding visitor behaviour and attraction and services planning, for continued use by the local stakeholders. These can be used for gaining insights that can facilitate a continuous sustainable route towards attracting tourists while preserving and protecting cultural heritage and the interests of the local community.

5. Scientific contribution developed during the project

- Mixed methods research design for measuring visitor engagement, which we have published in Chapter 12: Measuring rural tourist behaviour and engagement – inside the mind of the visitor”, in INCULTUM book: **“Visiting the Margins: Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries”**, (Eds. Borowiecki, K. Fresa, A. and Martín Civantos, J.M. 2024. In press. For more details see D2.4); including GPS tracking, paper and online questionnaires, and the use of QR codes.
- Peer-reviewed and published articles on GSM patterns and project survey responses, as well as tourists’ like clicking behaviour and local contexts in Gotland. These articles are available in Zenodo INCULTUM Community:
 - What you see is where you go: cruise tourists' spatial consumption of destination amenities: <https://zenodo.org/records/10951395>
 - Did liberal lockdown policies change spatial behaviour in Sweden? Mapping daily mobilities in Stockholm using mobile phone data during Covid-19: <https://zenodo.org/records/10950570>
 - Inequality in leisure mobility: An analysis of activity space segregation spectra in the Stockholm conurbation: <https://zenodo.org/records/10951438>
 - Leisure mobility changes during the COVID-19 pandemic – An analysis of survey and mobile phone data in Sweden: <https://zenodo.org/records/10955569>
- Article manuscript on spatiotemporal engagement submitted to a scientific journal on tourism, currently in the review process.
- [Developed and reported on an D4.4 Evaluation Framework for participatory modelling.](#)

References (pilot #10)

Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F., 2009. ‘Mode 3’ and ‘Quadruple Helix’: Toward a 21st Century Fractal Innovation Ecosystem. *International Journal of Technology Management*, 46(3-4), 201-234.

Martín Civantos, J. M., 2024. *Visiting the Margins: Innovative Cultural Tourism in European Peripheries*. London: Routledge

Steinitz, C., 2012. *A Framework for Geodesign: Changing Geography by Design*. Redlands, CA: ESRI Press.

3. Conclusion

Since its choice, during the drafting of the project proposal, the variety of the INCULTUM pilots was considered as a challenge to be faced. Now that we can expose the conclusions of the work carried out in the different areas, we can affirm that the peripheral areas of Europe have a great tourist potential that must be managed with the care they deserve. Tourism must be understood as a tool for these local communities that suffer the most from the difficulties (and the advantages) of being outside the major tourist circuits. The tangible and intangible historical heritage of all our pilots must be managed by the local communities themselves so that they, in turn, become aware of the value they possess and use all their resources for their own benefit.

INCULTUM has delivered a wide range of products and innovations that will help local communities to manage this hitherto little-known heritage. As well as the pilots themselves, the innovations achieved by each of the teams are very varied, from the use of IA in the transcription of grave inscriptions in Irish cemeteries (Pilot #9), to the analysis of tourist trajectories with GPS in the area of Pilot #10 (Sweden) or the influence of fee-for-service agreements between irrigation communities and municipalities for the management and conservation of historic and traditional irrigation systems in the Altiplano of Granada (Pilot #1).

With respect to the impact achieved (extensively described in D7.3 Updated plan for the impact, evaluation and exploitation of results) we consider it necessary here to highlight some last minute aspects. During the last consortium meeting (held on 11 April 2024) we had the opportunity to discuss the impact achieved by the pilots during the project. In the DoA there are a number of KPI's which in D7.3 are described and justified at length. However, a fruitful discussion led to a deeper reflection in some cases. Despite exceeding the ranges set in most of the initially drafted KPIs, some of them could not be analysed due to the way they were set. In the case of point 6 "Participatory approaches and social inclusion in the pilots", there are cases in which it has not been possible to measure the participation of women or the percentage of minority or immigrant populations in the pilots' activities. Although it is true that, for example, in the case of Albania, the Vlach population has participated in the activities organised by CeRPHAAL, collaborating with other administrations for the revaluation and empowerment of their culture and to make it known. In comparison, in other pilots there is no minority population that has been able to be involved in the activities carried out.

In another of the initially established KPIs, we can add some appreciations that could not be included in D7.3. This is the case of "Upscaling and exploitation", specifically in point "7. 1 Local authorities' spending in public services Increase in %

of the spending in the pilot areas"; in the case, for example, of pilot #1 Altiplano de Granada, the MEMOLab working group of the UGR has obtained funding from the Sierra Nevada Park of around 2 million euros to continue the work, initiated in the pilot, of restoring historical irrigation systems, as well as several projects from the Spanish Ministry of Ecological Transition to continue with the revaluation of these sustainable irrigation systems.

Also with respect to the KPI related to "New stakeholders joining the INCULTUM network" we can refer to the achievement of the French partner in its pilot #6 Bibracte, where it has achieved the creation of the prototype for the new cultural route developed as part of INCULTUM has attracted the attention of the French hiking federation. A proposal is now being drawn up to have the route approved as a national hiking trail (Sentier de Grande Randonnée de Pays), which would give it national recognition and visibility. A draft agreement is being studied between the French Hiking federation, the Grand Site de France Bibracte-Morvan des Sommets and the Parc naturel regional du Morvan, it should be finalised by the end of 2024. Also in this sense, also in pilot #1, the collaboration of a local association, Asociación Pasos, has been achieved, which has taken over from INCULTUM in the municipality of Galera, initially not included in the study area, but with which the collaboration will be maintained over time in order to continue working together.

In short, we can affirm that the INCULTUM pilots have made a great effort and a brilliant work during these years. Many of those responsible for the pilots agreed during the conversations held at the last meeting of the Consortium (Guadix, 11 April 2024) that after these years of effort it is now, when the project is coming to an end, that the local agents feel the desire and confidence to continue with the work, as the first results are now beginning to be seen. On the one hand, the sadness of the end of the project overwhelms the partners as unfortunately the project is administratively finished, but on the other hand, INCULTUM has served to plant seeds in the European peripheral territories that will surely bear fruit in the not too distant future.